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Legal Protection Of Genetic Resources And Traditional Knowledge Within The Framework Of Nigeria's Intellectual Property Regime

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ABSTRACT

Genetic resources and traditional knowledge are fundamental to the cultural identity, healthcare, agriculture, and spirituality of indigenous communities. Nevertheless, these resources are frequently exploited, commercialised, and patented without the consent or involvement of the communities that preserved them. This exploitation is encouraged by conventional intellectual property systems, which focus on individual ownership and written documentation, thereby failing to accommodate the communal, intergenerational, and oral nature of traditional knowledge. The unauthorised rebranding and commercial use of such knowledge amounts to bio-piracy and may be viewed as a form of cultural genocide because it threatens the existence and heritage of indigenous peoples. In Nigeria, the situation is heightened by a fragmented legal framework that neither recognises traditional knowledge as intellectual property nor adequately protects the rights of indigenous custodians. Existing patent and copyright laws provide only limited protection, while mechanisms for access and benefit-sharing, Free, Prior and Informed Consent (FPIC), and recognition of indigenous communities as legal persons remain largely absent. Although international instruments such as the Convention on Biological Diversity, the Nagoya Protocol, and the WIPO Treaty seek to address these injustices, Nigeria's implementation remains weak, making comprehensive legal reform, stronger enforcement, and equitable benefit-sharing essential for sustainability and cultural preservation.

Keywords: Genetic Resources, Traditional Knowledge, Intellectual Property, Bio-Piracy, Biocultural Heritage, Patent.

INTRODUCTION

One of the fundamental rights in Nigeria is the right to acquire, own and hold property.¹ This right is confirmed further by the prohibition of the alienability of private property by the government except under conditions that may be so specified by law.² While this provision appears to focus on tangible assets, the courts have extended its protection to intangible property.³ Intellectual property which includes genetic resources, as a form of intangible property can be interpreted to fall within the broader constitutional protection accorded to proprietary rights.

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¹ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended in 2023), s 43(1).

² CFRN, 1999 (n1) s 44

³ *Kolawale & Ors. v Oteri Holdings Ltd.* (2015) LPELR-51010(CA).

Genetic resources are the biological material of plants, animals, or microorganisms that have actual or potential value.⁴ Genetic resources such as bitter leaf and neem are deeply connected to indigenous knowledge systems and traditional healing practices. However, indigenous communities have long faced disputes over intellectual property (IP) rights when commercial entities patent or exploit these resources without obtaining consent or providing compensation to their traditional custodians.⁵

The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), to which Nigeria is a party, affirms the sovereign rights of states over their natural resources.⁶ The accompanying Nagoya Protocol to which Nigeria is a party builds on this by requiring 'prior informed consent' and 'fair and equitable benefit-sharing' when genetic resources are accessed.⁷ This was well highlighted in the WIPO Treaty on Intellectual Property, Genetic Resources and Traditional Knowledge.⁸ These frameworks, though grounded in environmental law, intersect with intellectual property regimes when biotechnological inventions are derived from such resources.

The issue becomes more legally complex with the inclusion of the World Trade Organization's TRIPS Agreement, which requires member states to grant patents for inventions in all fields of technology, provided they are new, inventive, and industrially applicable.⁹ Although the TRIPS Agreement appears neutral, its implementation often enables corporations to monopolise genetic resources without adequately recognising or compensating indigenous communities who developed the related traditional knowledge. This creates tension between TRIPS obligations and the protection of indigenous rights and traditional knowledge. Nigeria, while bound by TRIPS as a WTO member, also has constitutional and international human rights obligations to protect indigenous communities. Conventional intellectual property systems favour inventions that are novel, individually owned, and formally documented, whereas traditional knowledge is communal, passed down through generations, and mainly transmitted orally. As a result, traditional knowledge is often excluded from formal intellectual property protection and becomes vulnerable to exploitation and misappropriation. In the *Neem tree case*,¹⁰ a European company obtained a patent over a fungicidal product extracted from neem seeds. Indian farmers and scientists successfully challenged the patent on the grounds that the product had been used traditionally for generations. This case raises the issue that traditional knowledge is often invisible in modern patent examinations. Closer to home, Nigerian medicinal plants like *Vernonia amygdalina* (bitter leaf) and *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* (candlewood) have also been the subject of patent applications abroad, with little or no benefit to local communities.¹¹

Intellectual property rights in their current form are largely individualistic. This approach sits uneasily with indigenous interplay, where knowledge is inherited, collectively held, and culturally guarded. Conversely, the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) 2007 recognizes the right of indigenous communities to maintain, control, and protect their cultural heritage and traditional knowledge.¹² Therefore, when patents are granted over genetic resources without the consent of indigenous peoples, what is threatened is not only legal recognition, but also their dignity, identity, survival, and lived experiences.

⁴ Dan Sun, *Genetic Resources* (Springer, Dordrecht 1999) <https://link.springer.com/rwe/10.1007/1-4020-4494-1_148> accessed 29 June 2025.

⁵ Julian Inglis and others (eds), *Traditional Ecological Knowledge: Concepts and Cases* (International Program on Traditional Ecological Knowledge: International Development Research Centre 1993).

⁶ Convention on Biological Diversity, 1992, art. 15.

⁷ Nagoya Protocol 2010, arts 5 & 6.

⁸ GRATK 2024, Preamble.

⁹ Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) Agreement 1994, art. 27(1).

¹⁰ W R Grace and USDA, *Neem Tree Patent Case* (2000) T 0416/01 (EPO BoA).

¹¹ Kevin E Ebhojie, 'Patently Waiting for Sui Generis Rights: Systemic Biopiracy and Nigerian Traditional Knowledge in *Vernonia Amygdalina*' [2013] *SSRN Electronic Journal* 2, 2 <<http://www.ssrn.com/abstract=2285684>> accessed 12 July 2025.

¹² UNDRIP 2007, art. 31 and 32.

Nigeria presently lacks a comprehensive legal framework for safeguarding genetic resources. The Patents and Designs Act, Cap P2 LFN 2004 does not address traditional knowledge or benefit-sharing, while the National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (2016–2020) remains largely aspirational. This legal gap exposes indigenous communities to biopiracy and highlights the divide between conventional global intellectual property systems, which favour formal documentation and innovation, and traditional systems rooted in oral knowledge, communal memory, and generational wisdom.

BIOPROSPECTING, BIO-PIRACY AND MISAPPROPRIATION OF GENETIC RESOURCES AND TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE.

Bioprospecting, the exploration of biological materials and Traditional Knowledge (TK) for commercial or research purposes, has been a double-edged sword in Nigeria, offering opportunities for pharmaceutical drug discovery, agricultural improvement, and economic growth.¹³ Conversely, the use of Genetic Resources (GR) in Nigeria is often exploitative, involving lack of consent and no benefit-sharing with traditional holders despite their role in preserving such resources. Although Nigeria is rich in biodiversity, it lacks an effective Access and Benefit-Sharing (ABS) framework. While Nigeria is a party to the Nagoya Protocol, Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), and WIPO Treaty on Intellectual Property, Genetic Resources and Traditional Knowledge, these instruments have not been domesticated, creating a legal vacuum that empowers biopiracy and exploitation.

Foreign pharmaceutical companies, researchers, and even local firms frequently collect plant samples and indigenous ethnobotanical knowledge from rural communities under the guise of collaboration or development without proper documentation, disclosure, or compensation. These resources are often later used in commercial products or foreign patent filings without acknowledging or rewarding the indigenous communities, resulting in unjust enrichment at the expense of traditional knowledge holders.¹⁴

Moreover, local researchers who often work in partnership with international actors also engage in extractive practices, sometimes unintentionally but without ethical review frameworks that integrate ABS standards or community protocols, university-based research can mirror the same extractive dynamics seen in commercial biopiracy.¹⁵

Consider the case of Zobo (*Hibiscus sabdariffa*). It is a native Nigerian plant traditionally used for its health benefits, including blood pressure regulation and antimicrobial properties. For decades, it has been cultivated and used based on indigenous knowledge. However, patents related to its extracts and applications are now held by foreign private entities, including beverage and pharmaceutical companies, with no mechanism to link these patents back to the communities that developed and sustained the knowledge system.¹⁶ Another striking case is the Calabar bean (*Physostigma venenosum*), native to south-eastern Nigeria.¹⁷ Used in traditional rituals and medicine, the bean contains alkaloids with powerful pharmacological properties. Researchers identified physostigmine from this plant as a key compound in

¹³ G. Dutfeld, “A Critical Analysis on the Debate on Traditional Knowledge, Drug Discovery and patent based biopiracy”. *Global Intellectual Property Law and Policy* Vol 33, Issue No. 4, 2011, p238-244.

¹⁴ F. Emiri, *Unjustified Enrichment in the Civil and Common Law Traditions*, 2, available at <http://www.nigerianlawguru.com/articles/general/UNJUSTIFIED%20ENRICHMENT%20LAW%20IN%20THE%20CIVIL%20AND%20COMMON%20LAW%20TRADITIONS.pdf>, last visited on February 20 2026.

¹⁵ Doris Schroeder, ‘Justice and Benefit Sharing’ in Rachel Wynberg, Doris Schroeder and Roger Chennells (eds), *Indigenous Peoples, Consent and Benefit Sharing: Lessons from the San-Hoodia Case* (Springer Netherlands 2009) <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-3123-5_2> accessed 1 July 2025.

¹⁶ European Patent Office, ‘Use of the Hibiscus Sabdariffa extract in the preparation of a medicament’ 2003, <https://patents.google.com/patent/EP1316312A1/da#> accessed 2 July, 2025.

¹⁷ Juliet O Obi and others, ‘The Calabar Bean and Physostigmine: From African Ethno-Jurisprudence to Medicinal Discovery and Modern Pharmacotherapeutics’ (2023) (2) *American Journal of Pharmacotherapy and Pharmaceutical Sciences* 1 <<https://ajpps.org/the-calabar-bean-and-physostigmine-from-african-ethno-jurisprudence-to-medicinal-discovery-and-modern-pharmacotherapeutics/>> accessed 12 July 2025.

treating eye problems, glaucoma, dementia, constipation, epilepsy, cholera, hypertension and tetanus.¹⁸ Patents were filed in jurisdictions far from Nigeria.¹⁹ The communities from which the knowledge emerged received no formal acknowledgment, compensation, or opportunity to negotiate terms of access. Africa's biocultural landscape has long been a target of extractive research practices, often justified under the banner of innovation or development.²⁰ An illustration of this would be the Hoodia cactus. The Hoodia cactus can be traced to Kalahari Desert of South Africa and have been used by the San speaking tribes of the region for centuries.²¹ The San people traditionally used the Hoodia cactus to suppress hunger during long hunting expeditions, with this knowledge passed down orally through generations. In the 1990s, South Africa's Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) isolated the plant's appetite-suppressing compound and patented it without informing the San people, later licensing it to *Phytopharm*. Recognition of the San's Traditional Knowledge (TK) only came after public outcry in 2003.

Similarly, In the rainforests of Gabon and Cameroon, the Bwiti communities have long relied on the iboga plant for healing and spiritual rites for generations beyond memory.²² This knowledge was quietly harvested by Western scientists who isolated ibogaine, a potent alkaloid used in the treatment of addiction.²³ The scientists filed in the United States and Europe for ibogaine-based treatments, none of which acknowledged the Bwiti communities.²⁴ There was no prior informed consent, no community protocol, no return. This paper describes the experience of the Bwiti people as 'plunder with microscope'. There is also the one suffered by the Basotho people of Lesotho and parts of South Africa. These people have traditionally used Pelargonium sides, a hardy root plant, to treat respiratory infections.²⁵ To them, it is a common remedy that can be administered as tea.²⁶ German pharmaceutical companies extracted and patented Pelargonium-based formulations for treating bronchitis and sore throat, achieving significant commercial success. However, the local community was not involved, nor were profits shared or cultural origins acknowledged. Even though the patents were later challenged, most of the profits had already been gained elsewhere.

The turmeric case is often cited as the watershed moment in the global fight against biopiracy. For thousands of years, turmeric had been part of Indian households, a golden remedy passed down from generations to generations, healing wounds, curing infections, and enhancing recipes. But in 1995 the University of Mississippi Medical Centre secured a U.S. patent (No. 5,401,504) for the use of turmeric in wound healing.²⁷ The Indian government responded by challenging the patent through the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), using ancient Sanskrit manuscripts and a 1953 article in the Indian Medical Association Journal that demonstrated turmeric's historical medicinal use.²⁸ These cases

¹⁸ M O Aihokhai, J O Erhabor, and Macdonald Idu, 'Preliminary Studies on Physostigma Venenosum (Balf.) Seeds: Mineral Composition, Proximate and Phytochemical Analysis' (2019) (20) *African Scientist* 17.

¹⁹ F Coelho and J Birks, 'Physostigmine for Alzheimer's Disease' (2001) (2001) *The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* 1 <<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11405996/>> accessed 7 July 2025.

²⁰ Avantika Bhandari, 'Traditional Knowledge, Genetic Resources, Patent Law and Its Protection: A Legal Analysis of Africa, Latin America, and India. How India Can Protect It Fiercely' (PhD Thesis, Pennsylvania State University 2021) 134 <<https://insight.dickinsonlaw.psu.edu/sjd/20>>.

²¹ Jay McGown, *The Catch: Perspectives in Benefit Sharing* (Beth Burrows ed, 2nd ed, Edmonds Institute in cooperation with Third World Network 2006) 8.

²² Bhandari (n 20) 135.

²³ *ibid*.

²⁴ Jay McGown (n 21) 10.

²⁵ Rachel Wynberg, 'Biopiracy: Crying Wolf or a Lever for Equity and Conservation?' (2023) (52) *Research Policy* 1 <<https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048733322001950>> accessed 12 July 2025.

²⁶ Bhandari (n 20) 138.

²⁷ Bhandari (n 20) 138.

²⁸ Alyson Slack, 'TED Case Study: Turmeric' (*Geographic Indications and International Trade (GIANT)*, 2004) <<https://mandalaprojects.com/giant-project/turmeric.htm>> accessed 12 July 2025.

show ongoing risks when Traditional Knowledge (TK) linked to Genetic Resources (GR) is documented by outsiders and commercialised as innovation, leaving indigenous custodians invisible in legal and business systems.

Common issues include lack of Prior Informed Consent (PIC), absence of ABS agreements, and failure to recognize customary ownership. Without strong legal frameworks, companies evade penalties for bypassing communities, and once commercialization occurs, opportunities for redress are effectively closed.

LEGAL PROTECTION A NECESSITY:

Without a protective framework, genetic resources and traditional knowledge systems are highly vulnerable to piracy and extinction. These resources are central to the livelihoods and well-being of traditional communities, supporting sustainable ecosystem use and providing sustenance (Source of food security, health care provision, preservation of heritage, socio-cultural and economic development and sustainable development among others). Therefore, legal protection is essential for environmental conservation and for preserving the identities of indigenous custodians. Effective protection would help curb biopiracy and uphold the rights of indigenous peoples in line with Article 31 of UNDRIP, which guarantees their rights to protect their traditional knowledge and resources. Although Nigeria has rich biodiversity and traditional knowledge systems, its current intellectual property laws are inadequate to properly safeguard genetic resources linked to traditional knowledge.

EXISTING LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE PROTECTION OF TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND GENETIC RESOURCES IN NIGERIA AND ITS LIMITATION.

Nigeria's regulation of Genetic Resources (GR) and Traditional Knowledge (TK) remains fragmented, with no comprehensive law governing their ownership, access, use, and protection for indigenous communities.²⁹ Instead, the current system relies on a patchwork of sectoral laws, scattered across environmental regulations, intellectual property statutes, agricultural policies, and public health directives. This absence of a unified legal framework has created regulatory obstacle, where laws operate in parallel rather than in concert, often leading to contradictions, overlap, or enforcement limitation. Some of the existing legislations include:

A. Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended)

Genetic Resources (GR) and Traditional Knowledge (TK) are not expressly mentioned in the 1999 Constitution, but it provides an interpretive framework for sector-specific laws. Section 20 specifically obliges the state to protect and improve the environment, including water, air, land, forests, and wildlife.³⁰ It also included provisions for safeguarding cultural life and promoting scientific and technological research that supports cultural values.³¹ Nevertheless, these sections are part of Chapter II of the constitution, which contains non-justiciable directive principles.³² Nonetheless, these obligation sets the tone for biodiversity-related governance, including the preservation of community-managed ecosystems where most genetic resources are located.

The Constitution assigns to the federal government the authority to control and manage all natural resources found in, beneath, or on any land within Nigeria.³³ This clause creates tension between state control over natural and genetic resources and the rights of indigenous communities. If narrowly

²⁹ Ganiyu Yahaya, 'An Appraisal of Legal and Policy Framework on Conservation of Biodiversity in Nigeria: Challenges and Way Forward' (2024) (1) *LexScriptio A Journal of the Department of Jurisprudence and Public Law* 63 <<https://209.188.21.224/index.php/lexscriptio/article/view/131>> accessed 10 July 2025.

³⁰ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) 1999 (cap C23) s 20.

³¹ *Ibid* s 21.

³² *Ibid* 6(6)(c).

³³ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) 1999 (cap C23) s 44(3).

interpreted, it may allow exploitation without recognizing local knowledge or ensuring fair benefit-sharing.

B. Copyright Act.

The Copyright Act 2022 replaced the Copyright Act Cap C28 LFN 2004, introducing a broader framework for protecting intellectual creations in Nigeria. Although signed into law by President Muhammadu Buhari on 27 March 2023, it is cited as the Copyright Act, 2022.³⁴ While the Act primarily protects conventional works of authorship, it represents an important advancement in the acknowledgment and safeguarding of folklore expressions and traditional cultural expressions (TCEs), which are varieties of traditional knowledge.³⁵

Section 74 protects expressions of folklore as intergenerational works of indigenous communities, including oral traditions, music, dances, designs, and other cultural expressions, recognising them as legally protected Traditional Knowledge (TK) rather than public domain. Section 75 prohibits their unauthorised use without consent from the Nigerian Copyright Commission (NCC), with civil and criminal penalties for infringement.³⁶ Moreover, Section 76 provides for criminal liability in cases of serious infringement, including misappropriation or commercial exploitation without appropriate authorisation.³⁷

Furthermore, the Act gives the NCC the authority to oversee and administer rights related to expressions of folklore for the state and traditional communities.³⁸ The Act establishes registries, supervises collective management organisations, and provides dispute resolution mechanisms for communal rights. Although it does not expressly mention “Genetic Resources”, its protection of folklore indirectly safeguards Traditional Knowledge in agriculture, medicine, and ecology, especially where such knowledge is preserved through oral traditions, songs, stories, and customary practices.

C. Patents and Designs Act

In Nigeria, the safeguarding of inventions and industrial designs is regulated by the Patents and Designs Act. The Act lays down the legal basis for patenting inventions that are novel, result from inventive activity, and can be applied industrially.³⁹ Even though the Act does not explicitly refer to genetic resources or traditional knowledge, its practical implementation has considerable consequences for bio-innovation and indigenous intellectual contributions.

A key criticism of the Act is that it allows life forms and naturally occurring biological materials to be patented, including plant and microbial derivatives, even when they are based on long-standing Traditional Knowledge (TK) of indigenous communities.⁴⁰ As a result, patents may be granted for innovations derived from Traditional Knowledge (TK) without recognising or compensating indigenous knowledge holders. This encourages biopiracy, as the Act does not require disclosure of the origin of TK or Genetic Resources (GR) used in inventions.

The Act sets patentability requirements that an invention must be new, involve an inventive step, and be capable of industrial application. These requirements conflict with Traditional Knowledge (TK), which is intergenerational, not necessarily new, and often not compatible with standardized industrial application due to its flexible and context-specific nature.

³⁴ Copyright Act Cap P2 No. 56, of 2022 s 109.

³⁵ Ibid s 74.

³⁶ Ibid s 75.

³⁷ Ibid s 76.

³⁸ Ibid s 77–78.

³⁹ Copyright Act Cap P2 No. 56, of 2022 s 1

⁴⁰ Ruth L Okediji, ‘The International Intellectual Property Roots of Geographical Indications’ (82) *Chicago-Kent Law Review* 1329 <https://nationalaglawcenter.org/wp-content/uploads/assets/bibarticles/okediji_roots.pdf> accessed 7 July 2025.

Traditional Knowledge (TK) is collectively owned and cannot be attributed to a single individual, which conflicts with the Patent Act's focus on rewarding individual inventors. As a result, the Act is inadequate for effectively protecting TK and Genetic Resources (GR).

D. Trade Mark Act

A trade mark must be distinctive and registered in order to have intellectual property rights over it.⁴¹ A trademark must be distinctive and registered to enjoy intellectual property protection. Distinctiveness is the ability to differentiate products with which the trademark owner is or may be connected in the course of business from products with which no such connection exists, either generally or, in the event that the trademark is registered or proposed to be registered subject to restrictions, in relation to use within the scope of the registration. Additionally, the mark cannot be scandalous or misleading. Trade Marks Act states that it is illegal to register as a trademark or part that would be likely to mislead, confuse, or otherwise be ineligible for protection in a court of justice, be against the law or morality, or contain any scandalous design.⁴² The registration of a trade mark, give exclusive usage for a period of seven years and can be renewed upon application for a subsequent period fourteen years.⁴³ While this Act could be considered plausible, it only operate and can only protect traditional knowledge and its associated genetic resources when same is registered as registration is a condition for protection. Especially when commercialised or put in the public domain.⁴⁴ Thus, where there is no prior informed consent or disclosure at the point of registration, third parties can still harness genetic resources connected to traditional knowledge and secure registration of same. Further, traditional knowledge is communally held and passed from one generation to another while Trade Mark protection is personalized and for a limited period of time. Trademark law protects symbols, marks, and signs, not the knowledge or values embedded in Traditional Knowledge (TK) or Genetic Resources (GR).

E. Merchandise Mark Act.

This Act was is considered as one of the oldest Act that was established in 1916 to deal with trade description false marking and counterfeiting especially where those marks cause deceit and misrepresentation.⁴⁵ Thus, it criminalizes acts of falsification of registered trademarks.

This Act like the Trade Mark Act, fundamentally deals on marks that are registered in order to determine resemblance and infringement. While trade mark is only registered if the mark is novel, Traditional Knowledge are not novel as they are handed down from one generation to another. The Act like the Trade Mark Act, only protect the interest of individuals and not communal interest that is associated to traditional knowledge.

While there are legal framework within the Nigeria's intellectual property regime, they are bereaved of protecting genetic resources and traditional knowledge as they are tailored after conventional intellectual property model.

NONE INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LEGAL FRAME WORK.

A. National Biosafety Management Agency Act.

The National Biosafety Management Agency Act 2015 establishes the National Biosafety Management Agency (NBMA) as the principal regulatory body responsible for overseeing the safe use, transfer, and handling of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) and their products in Nigeria.⁴⁶ While the Act does not directly reference traditional knowledge, its implementation bears heavily on indigenous agricultural systems and genetic resources. Indigenous communities rely on local seed varieties and traditional farming techniques, many of which are susceptible to disruption from GMO introduction. The Act

⁴¹ Trade Mark Act, 1965, Cap T13, LFN 2004.

⁴² Trade Mark Act, 1965, Cap T13, LFN 2004 s 9 - 11

⁴³ Ibid s 9, 23

⁴⁴ Ibid s 9, 67

⁴⁵ Merchandise Mark Act, LFN 2004.

⁴⁶ National Biosafety Management Agency Act 2015 s 1 & 2.

recognises this indirectly by requiring risk assessments, public consultation, and socio-economic considerations in the approval of biosafety permits.⁴⁷ Moreover, Section 3(q) empowers the NBMA to collaborate with local and international agencies for the speedy realisation of the mandate of the Agency.

B. National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) Act.

The National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency Act (NESREA Act), enacted in 2007, establishes NESREA,⁴⁸ and designates it as the primary agency tasked with upholding all environmental laws and regulations in Nigeria.⁴⁹ NESREA statutory mandate includes biodiversity conservation, pollution control, and the protection of endangered species. In furtherance of its mandate, NESREA has developed the National Environmental (Access to Genetic Resources and Benefit Sharing) Regulations, 2009, under its enabling powers. These Regulations implement ABS principles and require any person or organisation seeking access to genetic resources in Nigeria to obtain a permit from NESREA.⁵⁰ Furthermore, the Regulations stipulate that access must rely on the prior informed consent of indigenous communities and that benefit-sharing agreements should be carried out in alignment with the customary laws and knowledge systems of these communities.⁵¹

C. National Agricultural Seed Council Act.

The National Agricultural Seed Council (NASC) Act establishes the NASC as the statutory body responsible for seed regulation, certification, and quality assurance in Nigeria. The main aim is to foster the generation and utilization of high-grade seeds in order to enhance agricultural productivity.⁵²

The Act is mainly aimed at formal seed systems, but it has important consequences for the conservation and utilization of plant genetic resources, especially in relation to traditional agriculture. Many rural farming communities in Nigeria conserve and develop local seed varieties using indigenous knowledge passed down over generations. These traditional seed systems are not adequately protected under the current NASC regime, which focuses on modern varieties bred in research institutions or private seed enterprises.

Given these shortcomings, there is a growing consensus on the need to reform the NASC Act to accommodate community seed systems, establish benefit-sharing guidelines, and align the seed sector with Nigeria's broader biodiversity obligations. This reform would also ensure constitutional harmony with Section 21 of the 1999 Constitution, which promotes Nigerian cultures and the dignity of traditional practice.

D. National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP) 2016

The primary tool for executing the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) in Nigeria is the National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP), which aligns with Article 6 of the CBD (Convention on Biological Diversity, 1992).⁵³ The first NBSAP was developed in 2001, and a revised edition was published in 2015 to align with the Aichi Biodiversity Targets and emerging biodiversity challenges.

The NBSAP recognises that Nigeria is endowed with vast biological and genetic resources, which form a critical part of the country's socio-economic development. It underscores the importance of indigenous and local communities in the conservation and sustainable use of genetic resources, and it explicitly recognizes traditional knowledge as an essential resource for biodiversity management and agricultural innovation.⁵⁴

⁴⁷ NBMA Act s 24 & 25.

⁴⁸ National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act 2007 s 1.

⁴⁹ NESREA 2007 s 7(b).

⁵⁰ National Environmental (Access to Genetic Resources and Benefit Sharing) Regulations, 2009 r 5.

⁵¹ ABS Regulations 2009 r 6.

⁵² National Agricultural Seeds Council Act 2019 s 15.

⁵³ Federal Ministry of Environment, *National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan 2016-2020* (Federal Republic of Nigeria 2016) ii <<https://www.cbd.int/doc/world/ng/ng-nbsap-v2-en.pdf>> accessed 7 July 2025.

⁵⁴ Ibid

A key aspect of the NBSAP is its focus on access and benefit-sharing (ABS) frameworks that align with the principles of prior informed consent (PIC) and mutually agreed terms.⁵⁵ The NBSAP, while not legally binding, offers a strategic policy framework and serves as a benchmark for the integration of biodiversity considerations into national development plans and legislation. It affirms the constitutional commitment to environmental protection,⁵⁶ and advocates for legislative measures that protect genetic resources and the traditional knowledge of indigenous peoples.

E. African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act.

The African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR), was endorsed by the Organization of African Unity in 1981 and became effective in 1986. Nigeria ratified the Charter in 1983 and domesticated it through the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act Cap A9 LFN 2004.

The Charter recognises both individual and collective rights and has been invoked in environmental, cultural, and indigenous rights jurisprudence. Article 17(2) provides for the right of every individual "to participate freely in the cultural activities of his community," while Article 24 guarantees the right of peoples "to a broadly satisfactory setting conducive to their development."

Additionally, Article 21 states that all peoples have the right to freely manage their wealth and natural resources, and in cases of spoliation, they are entitled to legal restitution.⁵⁷ This provision is essential regarding biopiracy and the exploitation of traditional knowledge, as it validates the rights of indigenous communities to safeguard and benefit from their ecological and intellectual contributions.

In its recent communications, the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights, has affirmed the cultural and environmental rights of indigenous communities. In *Centre for Minority Rights Development (Kenya) and Minority Rights Group International on behalf of Endorois Welfare Council v Kenya*,⁵⁸ the African Commission determined that the removal of the Endorois people from their ancestral territories breached multiple articles of the Charter, including those concerning their rights to culture, natural resources, and development.

F. Traditional Medicine Policy 2007

This policy arose from the need to integrate traditional medicine being a source of traditional knowledge into the National health system as it seeks to protect the interest of stakeholders of traditional medicine such as the traditional medicine practitioners from the various communities that have held the said knowledge over the years, regulatory agencies, researchers etc.⁵⁹ This policy is in conformity with the implementation of Regional strategy for the African Region on promoting the role of traditional medicine in health care system. It seeks the preservation of the cultural heritage, conservation of biodiversity and traditional knowledge associated to genetic resources.⁶⁰

The policy ensures the protection of intellectual property rights and indigenous traditional knowledge. Thus, it endures adequate prior consent, fair and equitable sharing as well as royalty returns to the holders of the said traditional knowledge.⁶¹ This policy aligns with the Convention on Biological Diversity and aims to preserve traditional knowledge through documentation. However, in practice, its implementation is limited because control over benefit-sharing and royalties rests with the government rather than the communities that own the genetic resources and traditional knowledge. This raises important concerns about ownership and custodianship.

⁵⁵ Federal Ministry of Environment, *National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan 2016-2020* (Federal Republic of Nigeria 2016) ii <<https://www.cbd.int/doc/world/ng/ng-nbsap-v2-en.pdf>> accessed 7 July 2025

⁵⁶ CFRN 1999 (as amended) s 20.

⁵⁷ African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights art 21 (1) & (2).

⁵⁸ (2009) AHRLR 75 (ACHPR 2009).

⁵⁹ Nkiruka Nwachukwu 'Law and Practice of Intellectual Property and Traditional Knowledge' (Princeton & Associate Publishing Co. Ltd. 2025)123.

⁶⁰ Traditional Medicine Policy for Nigeria 2007, (Pt 2)

⁶¹ Ibid Pt 1

INTERNATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE PROTECTION OF GENETIC RESOURCES AND TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE.

a. **Convention on Biological Diversity and the Nagoya Protocol**

The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), adopted in 1992 and ratified by Nigeria in 1994, is the principal global treaty for biodiversity conservation and sustainable use. It is based on three goals: (i) conserving biological diversity; (ii) ensuring sustainable use of its components; and (iii) fairly and equitably sharing benefits derived from the use of genetic resources.⁶²

The CBD affirms states' sovereign rights over their natural resources and stipulates that access to genetic resources must be based on prior informed consent (PIC) and mutually agreed terms (MAT).⁶³ Article 8(j) emphasizes the necessity of respecting, preserving, and maintaining the traditional knowledge, innovations, and practices of local and indigenous communities that are pertinent to biodiversity.

Adopted in 2010 as a supplementary agreement to the CBD, the Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization bolsters the ABS framework. It requires parties to implement legislative and administrative measures to guarantee a fair sharing of benefits derived from the use of genetic resources and associated traditional knowledge with the communities that provide them.⁶⁴

Nigeria ratified the Nagoya Protocol in 2014 and has since enacted the National ABS Regulations 2009 (amended in line with Protocol requirements) and **incorporated access and benefit-sharing provisions into policy documents such as the NBSAP 2016-2020**. Nigeria's legislative initiatives aimed at safeguarding traditional knowledge and guaranteeing fairness in the use of its genetic resources should continue to be fundamentally influenced by the CBD and the Nagoya Protocol.

b. **United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples 2007**

The United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP), adopted by the UN General Assembly in 2007, is a landmark human rights instrument recognising the cultural, social, economic, and political rights of indigenous peoples. Although not legally binding, UNDRIP is considered a soft-law instrument with strong moral and political weight. Article 31 confirms that indigenous peoples have the right to maintain, control, protect, and develop their cultural heritage, traditional knowledge, and traditional cultural expressions, including their sciences, technologies, and genetic resources. It also affirms their entitlement to intellectual property rights over such knowledge and resources.⁶⁵

Furthermore, Articles 26–29 recognise the rights of indigenous communities to own and control their lands, territories, and resources, and require states to obtain free, prior, and informed consent (FPIC) before exploiting such resources. These provisions are highly relevant to the governance of genetic resources in Nigeria, particularly in relation to bioprospecting, seed sovereignty, and traditional medicine. Although Nigeria abstained from the 2007 vote on UNDRIP, its principles are increasingly reflected in international environmental and intellectual property (IP) norms and are viewed as emerging customary international law. As a result, they carry persuasive authority in shaping Nigeria's indigenous rights framework.

c. **Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) 1994**

The Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS), administered by the World Trade Organization (WTO), establishes minimum standards for the protection and enforcement of intellectual property rights among WTO member states. As a member of the WTO, Nigeria is required to comply with TRIPS obligations.

⁶² Convention on Biological Diversity 1992 art 1.

⁶³ *Ibid* art 15.

⁶⁴ Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from Their Utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity 2011 arts 5–7.

⁶⁵ UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP), 2007 art 31.

Although TRIPS Agreement does not explicitly mention genetic resources or traditional knowledge, its provisions on patents, plant variety protection, and copyright have implications for these areas. Under Article 27.3(b), WTO members may exclude plants and animals from patentability, but they must still provide protection for plant varieties through patents, an effective *sui generis* system, or a combination of both.⁶⁶ This provision raises concerns about the compatibility of TRIPS with the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the Nagoya Protocol, especially in relation to biopiracy and the absence of benefit-sharing requirements under TRIPS. Developing countries have proposed reforms to TRIPS to introduce mandatory disclosure of origin, proof of prior informed consent, and benefit-sharing obligations in patent applications involving genetic material.⁶⁷

While the TRIPS Council has not yet approved such amendments, Nigeria has the option to establish a *sui generis* system for safeguarding traditional knowledge and to integrate ABS principles into its IP framework.

d. WIPO Treaty on intellectual property, Genetic Resources and Traditional Knowledge,

The WIPO Treaty on Intellectual Property, Genetic Resources and Traditional Knowledge (GRATK Treaty), adopted in 2024, aims to improve transparency, efficiency, and quality in the patent system. It helps prevent erroneous patents over inventions lacking novelty or inventiveness involving genetic resources and traditional knowledge by requiring adequate disclosure before patent grant. The treaty also promotes anti-biopiracy through a mandatory patent disclosure requirement, obliging applicants to disclose the source and origin of genetic resources used.⁶⁸ This is done by the information officer.

This treaty represents hope for Traditional Knowledge and genetic Resources it creates a more comprehensive IP regime which takes into account the diverse and peculiar needs of various communities as well as recognizes and promote their rights as it also encourages innovation driven by traditional knowledge.⁶⁹ This indeed is an attempt to harmonize traditional knowledge and Intellectual Property. While this treaty is considered a laudable means of protection of traditional knowledge and Genetic Resources, it is yet to be domesticated by Nigeria.

PATHWAYS FOR REFORM

Nigeria's Intellectual Property (IP) system for protecting Genetic Resources (GR) and Traditional Knowledge (TK) is fragmented, with no unified framework, conflicting laws, and weak implementation. Challenges such as bio-piracy, poor enforcement, non-domestication of international instruments, and low public awareness hinder effective protection. There is therefore a need for reform, including a shift toward a *sui generis* legal regime and innovative mechanisms like a Traditional Knowledge Digital Library and an IP tribunal.

i. Towards a *Sui Generis* Law

The current Intellectual Property (IP) regime is inadequate for protecting Traditional Knowledge (TK) and Genetic Resources (GR), highlighting the need for a *sui generis* legal framework tailored to their unique nature rather than forcing them into Western IP categories. This approach would better protect indigenous communities by preventing unauthorized privatization of their knowledge and addressing gaps in existing IP systems. A *sui generis* law would recognize TK and GR as standalone protected categories,

⁶⁶ Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights 1994, 1869 UNTS 299, Annex 1C to the WTO Agreement art 27.3(b).

⁶⁷ Biswajit Dhar and RV Anuradha, 'Access, Benefit-Sharing and Intellectual Property Rights' (2004) (7) *Journal of World Intellectual Property* 597 <<https://heinonline.org/HOL/Page?handle=hein.journals/jwip7&id=580&div=&collection=>>.

⁶⁸ Basic Proposal for International Legal Instrument Relating to Intellectual Property, Genetic Resources and Traditional Knowledge Associated with Genetic Resources 2024, Article 3.

⁶⁹ Manisha Singh and Shivi Gupta, 'Analyzing WIPO's Landmark Treaty on Intellectual Property, Genetic Resources, and Associated Traditional Knowledge' (Lexology, 21 June 2024) <<https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=6912a7ab-aaf3-4fd7-883e-5127f390cf20>> accessed 2 July 2024

based on collective ownership, oral traditions, and customary practices, rather than requiring originality or inventiveness.⁷⁰

The proposed framework would make Access and Benefit-Sharing (ABS) a legal obligation, requiring Prior Informed Consent (PIC) and Mutually Agreed Terms (MAT) before accessing Genetic Resources (GR) or Traditional Knowledge (TK), with fair benefits such as royalties, infrastructure, co-authorship, or conservation support.

It would also introduce the economic valuation of TK to ensure fair compensation and stronger bargaining power for indigenous communities through consultation-based valuation guidelines. In addition, it would require mandatory disclosure of origin in patent applications and product approvals to prevent misappropriation and ensure transparency.

ii. Harmonising Statutes with Customary Norms

Meaningful reform requires more than statutory changes; it must bridge the gap between formal law and customary practices. Since Nigerian communities already have established systems for managing resources and Traditional Knowledge (TK), reforms should recognize customary law as a valid legal source. Future laws should therefore be flexible and adaptable, allowing community-specific protocols rather than imposing rigid statutory frameworks.

iii. Strengthening Enforcement through Institutional Coordination

Effective reform depends on strong enforcement, as weak implementation undermines even well-drafted laws. Nigeria's institutional framework is currently fragmented and under-resourced, requiring clearer coordination. A proposed solution is the creation of a single National Biodiversity and Knowledge Authority to serve as the lead agency for Traditional Knowledge (TK) and Genetic Resources (GR), handling permits, Access and Benefit-Sharing (ABS), litigation support, and databases, while reducing overlap with agencies like NESREA, NOTAP, and NBMA. Inter-agency coordination should be strengthened through a National Coordination Committee on Genetic Resources, involving relevant ministries, agencies, community leaders, and civil society to ensure consistent interpretation and shared responsibilities. Enforcement must also be accessible, with communities given direct complaint and redress mechanisms through local officers or state-level offices. Ultimately, empowering indigenous communities alongside coordinated institutions is key to ensuring compliance and protecting rights effectively.

iv. Embedding Human Rights in Regulatory Design

Regulations should reflect societal values, with Human Rights forming the foundation of any framework on Traditional Knowledge (TK) and Genetic Resources (GR). This requires shifting focus from merely protecting economic interests to safeguarding dignity, culture, and community rights. Current Nigerian laws on biodiversity and IP emphasize control and compliance, with little attention to justice or marginalized communities, despite the significant stakes for traditional knowledge holders. New laws should therefore recognize rights to culture, participation in development, and fair benefit from one's resources and inventions, drawing on instruments such as the African Charter, UNDRIP, and the Nagoya Protocol. A rights-based approach enhances legitimacy, builds trust, and ensures equitable benefits for local communities.

v. Establishment of a Traditional Knowledge Digital Library (TKDL)

A key and implementable reform is the establishment of a Traditional Knowledge Digital Library (TKDL), a secure, structured database for documenting Traditional Knowledge (TK) and biodiversity practices. As shown in India, a TKDL serves both defensive and protective purposes by preventing bio-piracy and patent fraud, while helping communities assert ownership over their knowledge.

A Nigerian TKDL would record knowledge in local languages, translate it into international patent classification systems, and make it accessible to global patent offices to block invalid patents using prior

⁷⁰ J. Janewa Osei Tutu, 'Emerging Scholars Series: A Sui Generis Regime for Traditional Knowledge: The Cultural Divide in Intellectual Property Law' (2011) 15 Marq. *Intellectual Property L. Rev.* 147 <<https://scholarship.law.marquette.edu/iplr/vol15/iss1/3> > accessed 17 February 2025.

art. However, it must remain community-driven, with control over what is shared, how it is accessed, and protection for sacred knowledge through tiered access and safeguards. Its implementation would require legislation, infrastructure, and ethical guidelines, but it would strengthen Nigeria's protection of TK and Genetic Resources (GR) and promote cultural and knowledge sovereignty.

vi. Establishment of a Specialised Intellectual Property Tribunal

Nigeria's general court system is poorly equipped to handle complex Intellectual Property (IP) disputes involving Traditional Knowledge (TK) and Genetic Resources (GR), largely due to limited technical expertise and resulting delays. To address this, a Specialised Intellectual Property Tribunal should be created to handle IP, biocultural rights, Access and Benefit-Sharing (ABS), TK, and GR matters. The tribunal would provide expert, faster, and more flexible adjudication, with simplified procedures that allow oral testimony, community participation, culturally relevant evidence, and class actions. It should be composed of legal, scientific, and indigenous knowledge experts, and may also serve as a reference body in international biopiracy disputes. The tribunal would function as an independent quasi-judicial institution under the IP Commission or Ministry of Justice, ensuring stronger protection and recognition of TK and GR rights.

CONCLUSION:

Innovation can also be found in Traditional Knowledge (TK) held within communities, yet Nigeria's Intellectual Property (IP) system prioritizes formal, individual, and novel inventions over collective, orally transmitted knowledge. The current framework, including the Patents and Designs Act, provides no protection or benefit-sharing for TK and Genetic Resources (GR). Although Nigeria has ratified key instruments like the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the Nagoya Protocol, and the WIPO Treaty on IP, Genetic Resources and TK, they have not been domesticated, and there is no effective Access and Benefit-Sharing (ABS) regime. This enables bioprospecting without proper consent, leaving communities as sources of innovation but not beneficiaries. Reform must therefore be bold and inclusive, recognizing TK as a vital, living resource tied to identity, survival, and innovation, and thus, shifting IP law toward protecting what must be preserved, not only what can be patented.